

Tesla Plasma Field Pilot Test

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The Study

This study is designed to test whether or not a specific Tesla Plasma technology has an effect upon the physiology during a 13-minute expose while playing Sudoku. As a randomized double-blind study neither the six subjects nor the designer who conducted the experiment knew which table contained the Placebo and which table contained the Treatment. These subjects were all practitioners of TM and current members of the same University.

Method

Procedure

While getting connected to the devices, subjects were asked six questions on a Likert scale of 1 to 10 to identify how they were feeling that day, how they feel about drawing on a white board, their level of knowledge with Sudoku, their anxiety level when it comes to tests and their anxiety level related to non-test activities like playing Sudoku.

Each subject was tested independently for 13 minutes at one random assigned table, then went to the drawing board for three minutes of creative drawing, then followed up with 13 minutes at the other table.

The order of tables was randomized. Under one table was the Tesla device. Under the other was a placebo.

Test Instrumentation

Up Alpha coherence, EDA and breath rate were recorded with a Nexus-10.

Results

Figure 1 shows the average alpha coherence when completing the Sudoku at Table A (placebo) and at Table B (Tesla).

Coherence was marginally lower when completing the puzzle at the Tesla table, but the effect sizes are very small ($d=.07$).

Fig. 1 - Alpha Coherence of Tesla Plasma Field and Placebo.

Figure 2 below shows levels of EDA and Breath rate when completing the Sudoku at Table A (placebo) and at Table B (Tesla). In this figure, EDA levels were lower when completing the Sudoku at Table B (Tesla). This was a medium effect size ($d= 0.4$). In contrast, breath rate was higher when completing the Sudoku at Table B (Tesla) ($d= -.26$).

Figure 2 show EDA and Delta for placebo (blue) and treatment (red).

The fig. 2 EDA red graph is lower, and the red Breath/minute is higher.

Figure 3 presents the magnitude of breath in as reflected in delta power when completing the Sudoku at Table A (placebo) and at Table B (Tesla). Delta power (breath power) was substantially lower when completing the Sudoku at Table B (Tesla) ($d = .67$).

Fig. 3 Delta power of the breath rate reflecting magnitude of breath volume.

Figure 4 presents the Pearson's Correlations among all the variables. None were correlated suggesting that each measure is giving independent information.

Results

Correlation

Pearson's Correlations

Variable		Co Table A	EDA Table A	Delta	Delta_11	Co Table B	EDA Table B	Delta_20	Delta_25
1. Co Table A	Pearson's r	—							
	p-value	—							
2. EDA Table A	Pearson's r	0.348	—						
	p-value	0.499	—						
3. Delta	Pearson's r	0.643	-0.293	—					
	p-value	0.168	0.573	—					
4. Delta_11	Pearson's r	-0.389	-0.663	-0.111	—				
	p-value	0.445	0.151	0.834	—				
5. Co Table B	Pearson's r	0.884	0.031	0.602	0.071	—			
	p-value	0.019	0.954	0.206	0.894	—			
6. EDA Table B	Pearson's r	0.702	0.861	0.075	-0.797	0.360	—		
	p-value	0.120	0.028	0.888	0.058	0.483	—		
7. Delta_20	Pearson's r	0.585	-0.422	0.852	0.276	0.761	-0.140	—	
	p-value	0.223	0.405	0.031	0.597	0.079	0.791	—	
8. Delta_25	Pearson's r	-0.238	-0.677	-0.026	0.948	0.208	-0.683	0.293	—
	p-value	0.650	0.140	0.962	0.004	0.693	0.135	0.573	—

Discussion

These data show that coherence was not different, but EDA levels, and breath rate and breath volume (delta power) substantially varied when completing a Sudoku puzzle at Table B (Tesla) compared to Table A (placebo). Lower EDA levels signify major reductions in sympathetic tone. However, lower EDA levels would lead to slower breath rate=not higher- and lower breath volume (which was seen).

This double-blind study yielded medium to large effect sizes in EDA and breath rate and volume. This suggests that the Tesla devices effects physiological functioning. Blood flow increased and blood volume decreased.

Future research should directly test the prediction that these devices will affect blood flow and immune functioning. The data gathered here does not readily relate to these predictions.

Also, future research should first include pilot testing of blood flow and immune functioning, and then from the magnitude of the effect sizes determine the number of subjects needed for statistical significance. Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) instrumentation would be sufficient for more in-depth testing.

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